

The Relationship Between Parenting Patterns and Adolescents' Learning Interests in the Online Learning Process During the Covid-19 Pandemic

Promotion and Prevention in
Mental Health (PPMH) Journal

Volume 4, Issue 1,
May 2025
e - ISSN : 2807-7148
p - ISSN : 2807-7784

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DOI:

10.63983/xgxx9939

Article Information:

Received : 26 April 2025

Revised : 28 May 2025

Accepted : 30 May 2025

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You Have to Know!

1. This study examines the relationship between parenting patterns and adolescents' learning interest during online learning in the COVID-19 pandemic.
2. Findings show a weak but significant relationship between parenting styles and adolescent learning interest (eta 0.213–0.261).
3. Parenting patterns influence adolescents' motivation and psychological development during online learning, suggesting the need for deeper exploration of cultural and environmental factors.

Abstract

Introduction: The COVID-19 pandemic has impacted the education sector, leading to the adoption of online learning through various applications. Online learning can affect learning interest, which can cause boredom in adolescents. Parenting patterns influence the sustainability of the online learning process, especially in children's interest and motivation in forming learning habits. This study aims to determine the relationship between parenting patterns and adolescent learning interest in the online learning process amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. **Methods:** The research methodology employed in this study is a correlational analysis survey using a cross-sectional approach, and the sample was selected using simple random sampling. The study involved 93 respondents, including parents and adolescents aged 13-18 years, from Wirokerten Village, Banguntapan District, Bantul Regency, the Special Region of Yogyakarta. The research data analysis used the eta correlation test and was interpreted using the Pearson correlation coefficient scale. **Results:** The study findings revealed a weak relationship between the two variables, with the eta correlation test results ranging from 0.213 to 0.261. In conclusion, this study affirms the existence of a relationship between parenting patterns and adolescents' learning interests in the online learning process during the COVID-19 pandemic. **Conclusions:** It is suggested that future researchers focus on exploring factors that influence parenting patterns, such as cultural and environmental factors, in the psychological development of adolescents. Additionally, analyzing cross-data between parenting patterns and psychological factors, as well as considering the perspectives of both parents and children, could provide valuable insights for further research.

Keyword: Learning Interests, Parenting Patterns, Learning Interests, Online Learning, COVID-19 Pandemic

How to Cite:

Nurazizah, A., Windarwat, H. D., Ningrum, E. H., & Wulandari, S. M. (2025). The Relationship Between Parenting Patterns and Adolescents' Learning Interests in the Online Learning Process During the Covid-19 Pandemic. *Promotion and Prevention in Mental Health Journal*, 4(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.37287/xgxx9939>

1. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has led many countries to adopt distance learning for their

students.^{1,2} The education sector is transitioning from conventional face-to-face learning to online learning through applications.³ The Ministry of

Education of the Republic of Indonesia issued Decree Number 4 of 2020, which contains an overview of the implementation process and objectives of online learning during the pandemic.³⁻⁷ Implementing online learning is considered to have similarities, and students feel a better experience from both learning methods, while 37% of them feel that online learning is precious.³

Data from the Wahana Visi Indonesia study conducted in May 2020 showed that 40% of students felt bored, 419 children felt unpleasant about online learning, and 35% worried about falling behind in subjects.⁸ A high level of anxiety in adolescents was found, with a percentage of 54% during the COVID-19 period. In Bantul, 76.6% of students feel bored with online learning. This can result in students not using their time optimally, so that learning becomes less effective.¹ The high level of anxiety can be caused by a lack of literacy and information that accompanies the overwhelming amount of news in the media.⁹ Additionally, a literature review provided evidence of increased stress and anxiety related to changes in learning methods during the pandemic. Research stated that 89% of respondents admitted to having difficulty concentrating,¹⁰ and 82% expressed concerns regarding the academic burden that would be borne due to the pandemic.¹¹ Furthermore, the pandemic has led to confusion, decreased concentration ability, and diminished memory.¹² These challenges endanger the future of today's young generation and limit human resource development.²

Parents are required to undergo a learning process to enhance their competence and effectiveness in fulfilling their parental roles. Many parents are unprepared and face additional tasks, including the availability of information technology facilities and their lack of understanding of using information technology.¹³ Parents' obstacles during online learning include their inability to understand the material, lack of interest in learning for children, and time to accompany children.¹⁴ As reported from Kompas.com, the Tanoto Foundation conducted a survey of 1,712 parents and found that 34% of parents were impatient and bored with accompanying their children in the learning process, 28% of parents found it challenging to explain the material to their children, and 24% found it difficult to understand the content of the material given.¹⁵ This online learning forces all parties, from teachers to the readiness of students and parents, to play an active role in the learning process.¹⁶ On the other hand, online learning can also increase interest in

learning, expand learning opportunities, and develop students' sense of autonomy. Additionally, it can provide learning opportunities at a lower cost.¹⁶ However, the lack of social support from the surrounding environment and cognitive inequality can affect students' emotional and motivational states.² This can be a problem and a challenge that needs to be faced from now on.¹⁶⁻¹⁸ Therefore, there needs to be a strategy in place to maximize the positive impacts and limit the negative impacts of online learning.

In addition to the same learning facilities, online learning that tends to stare at the screen without any physical interaction tends to make teenagers bored.¹⁹ Many students experience low to moderate boredom.²⁰ According to another study, 68% of elementary, middle, and high school students said they were bored with online learning due to various obstacles.²¹ Boredom with online learning results in changes in students' attitudes, including feeling lazy, easily angered, and frustrated every time they have to undergo learning.²²

Boredom is a condition that can be caused by ongoing stress that is appropriately managed, leading a person to lose interest in a specific activity.²⁰ The decline in enthusiasm for learning was found in this study,²³ where 52.6% of 344 students stated that their enthusiasm for learning had decreased, and 61.1% stated that it was difficult to find a conducive environment and time to participate in learning.²³ This indicates that over time, the online learning process can lead to anxiety, boredom, and decreased interest in learning among children.

Interest in learning refers to the desire to know or understand something to achieve positive learning outcomes. Interest in learning shows feelings of preference, interest, and attention that can influence a person's learning behavior until learning goals are achieved.²⁴ Two factors influence interest in learning: internal factors in the form of physical and emotional conditions, psychological conditions, perceptions, motivations, talents, and strengths to master knowledge.²⁵ Meanwhile, external factors can influence both parents' role in being ready to help children if there are problems, facilitating the equipment needed, and creating support and a comfortable atmosphere in the learning process.^{25,26} External factors originating from schools include teaching methods, curriculum, facilities, infrastructure, teaching resources and media, and relationships with friends and teachers.²⁵ Moreover the last is the community environment,

namely relationships with peers, community activities, and the residential environment.²⁵ Increasing interest in learning can be done by modifying external factors. Among the existing external factors, parents' role and support are important because students are always at home during the pandemic.

The application of parenting patterns aims to foster a child's independence and responsibility.²⁷ On the other hand, parenting patterns are also applied to form a child's personality and character.^{28,29} Fadhilah's research analysis indicates that parenting patterns are influenced by environmental factors, age, education, marital relationships, and culture. Research suggests that parenting patterns employed while children are learning online are believed to influence their learning habits.³⁰ Positive parenting patterns towards children can affect learning outcomes and are related to children's independence, especially in adolescence.³¹ The attitudes and treatment of parents who support learning, such as the attention given by parents regarding learning, are very much needed because children still need encouragement to achieve learning independence.²⁹ Therefore, it can be inferred that parenting patterns can impact children's learning process, particularly in cultivating an interest in learning, as this significantly influences children's emotions and behavior during the learning process.

Parenting patterns will be related to the online learning process, where parents have a role in accompanying children in the learning process. This study was conducted to determine the relationship between parenting patterns and adolescent interest in the online learning process during the COVID-19 pandemic.

2. METHODS

2.1. Study Design and Sample

The researcher used a correlational analysis survey method and applied a cross-sectional approach. The researcher conducted data collection simultaneously on 93 respondents at a single point in time. The study was conducted in Wirokerten Village, Bantul, DIY, in December 2021. The population was 1,371 pairs of parents and adolescent children. A sample of 93 respondents was selected using a simple random sampling method. The parent variable (independent) and the adolescent learning interest variable (dependent)

2.2. Data Collection

Data collection techniques were carried out with pre-tests and post-tests in observing signs and symptoms of hallucinations based on SDKI, namely based on signs of major and minor symptoms that were observed changes every day in hallucination patients. The research instrument was the PSQ (Parenting Style Questionnaire) questionnaire as a measuring tool for parenting patterns and the Online Student Engagement Scale (OSE) questionnaire to measure children's learning interests.

2.3. Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using univariate and bivariate analysis with the Eta correlation test.

3. RESULTS

Table 1 indicates that most respondents came from Dusun Sampangan (28%). The dominant parental relationship is the mother (68.8%), and most parents are between 45-54 years old (48.4%). The majority of respondents, 40.9%, do not work or are housewives. The highest level of education is senior high school (44.1%), and the majority of family income is in the range of IDR 600,000 to IDR 1,500,000 (38.7%). The most extensive distribution of children's ages is 17 years old (25.8%), with the largest gender being female (59.1%). Most respondents who filled out the questionnaire came from grade 12 (28%).

Table 2 shows that most respondents' parenting patterns applied are democratic parenting patterns (60.2%). Table 3 reveals that most parent-child relationships, both fathers and mothers, have the highest results for applying democratic parenting patterns. Table 4 demonstrates that the skill subscale obtained a mean value of 3.60 (SD 0.65). The emotion subscale showed a mean value of 3.54 (SD 0.62). The participation subscale had a mean value of 3.76 (SD 0.61). A mean value of 3.75 (SD 0.76) was obtained for the implementation subscale.

Table 5 shows that authoritarian parenting has the highest average on children's learning interests, with a mean value on each subscale, namely skills (K) 4.05, emotions (E) 3.92, participation (Pa) 3.82, and implementation (P) 3.87. The following most successful result is democratic parenting. The lowest average was found in permissive parenting. Table 6 indicates that the eta correlation test cross-tabulation results obtained a

statistical value of 0.213 - 0.261, concluding that there is a weak relationship between the two

Table 1. Respondent Characteristics (n=63)

Respondent Characteristics		f	%
Address	Sampang	26	28,0
	Botokenceng	8	8,6
	Grojogan	12	12,9
	Kepuh	16	17,2
	Glondong	11	11,8
	Tobratan	4	4,3
	Wirorkerten	6	6,5
	Mutihan	10	10,8
Relationship with Child	Father	29	31,2
	Mother	64	68,8
Parents' Age	25 – 34 years	4	4,3
	35 – 44 years	33	35,5
	45 – 54 years	45	48,4
	≥ 55 years	11	11,8
Occupation	Unemployed / Housewife	38	40,9
	Farmer / Laborer	19	20,4
	Self-employed	25	26,9
	PNS / TNI	10	10,8
	Retiree	1	1,1
Education	Elementary School	13	14,0
	Junior High School	13	14,0
	Senior High School	41	44,1
	University	26	28,0
Family Income	< 600 thousand	13	14,0
	600 thousand – 1,5 million	36	38,7
	1,5 million – 5 million	29	31,2
	> 5 million	15	16,1
Child's Age	13 years	18	19,4
	14 years	12	12,9
	15 years	15	16,1
	16 years	8	8,6
	17 years	24	25,8
	18 years	16	17,2
Child's Gender	Male	38	40,9
	Female	55	59,1
Grade	7	17	18,3
	8	9	9,7
	9	17	18,3
	10	8	8,6
	11	16	17,2
	12	26	28,0

variables.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution Based on Parenting Pattern Variables (n=63)

Parenting Style	f	%
Democratic	56	60,2
Authoritarian	4	4,3

4. DISCUSSION

Parenting Patterns in the Online Learning Process During the COVID-19 Pandemic

The study revealed that the most common parenting style used was democratic parenting, followed by permissive parenting and authoritarian parenting. Other results stated that democratic parenting patterns had a percentage of 49%, the most widely applied by parents.³² Dominant parenting pattern used by guardians was democratic parenting patterns, which influence children's learning inspiration. Democratic parenting patterns can improve children's character, discipline, and learning habits.³³ During the COVID-19 pandemic, parents must still prioritize children's learning rights according to their interests, talents, abilities, and needs.

Democratic parenting patterns, also known as flexible parenting patterns, focus on control and affection.³⁴ According to Baumrind's parenting style theory, democratic parenting is called flexible because it can adapt to circumstances, provide support, and set boundaries simultaneously. Democratic parenting is successful in forming children to have high self-esteem, achieve positive results and good academic achievement, have better social skills, and have low problem behavior in children.³⁵ In a study by Dr. Thomas G. Power children can adapt and control themselves well with democratic parenting.³⁶ It is known that the application of democratic parenting is oriented towards problems and rational attitudes; this creates responsiveness and negotiation between children and parents so that they can get good and positive results.

The choice of parenting style can be adjusted to family conditions. Families with complex economies will need more authoritarian parenting because many limitations must be considered.³⁷ Applying parenting does not necessarily have to be absolute in one type of parenting style. Parents could combine two or more situations.³⁸ Baumrind's theory states that a child's personality is formed from each parenting pattern they receive during parental care. Hurlock's theory states that each type

Table 3. Frequency Distribution of Parenting Pattern Variables Based on Relationship with Children (n=63)

Relationship with Children	Family Support Category					
	Democratic		Authoritarian		Permissive	
	f	%	f	%	F (N)	P (%)
Father	16	55,2	0	0	13	44,8

Table 4. Frequency Distribution Based on Learning Interest Variables of Adolescent Children

Variables	Sub-scale	Mean	SD
Interest in Learning	Skills	3,60	0,65
	Emotion	3,54	0,62
	Participation	3,76	0,61
	Implemetation	3,75	0,76

of parenting pattern has a role and influence on a child's behavior.³⁸ Given that parenting patterns are closely related to the formation of a child's character, emotional intelligence, and habits, it is necessary to consider and choose the correct parenting pattern.

Learning Interest in Online Learning Process. During the COVID-19 Pandemic

The learning interest variable is measured using four subscales: skills, emotions, participation, and implementation. Based on the research conducted, the mean and Standard Deviation results for each subscale were obtained with the same value (homogeneous). It was found that the results differed from Apriyanto's (2020) research, where the

mean score for learning interest was 5.8 (58%), with a maximum value of 10.³⁹ In addition, it also differs from Purnama's (2016) research because the mean value obtained was 3.3634 (67.26%) with a maximum value of 5.

One crucial factor in the learning process that influences learning success is interest. Interest in learning is a form of obedience carried out through learning planning and severe effort and initiative in learning.⁴⁰ In addition, interest is formed due to habits of learning participation, activeness, enthusiasm, and experience from learning.⁴¹ Elizabeth Hurlock said that the characteristics of interest in learning include interest growth along with physical and mental development, depending on learning activities and opportunities, limited

Table 5. Distribution of Respondents Based on the Relationship between Parenting Patterns and Adolescent Learning Interests (n=63)

Variables		Interest in Learning			
		K	E	Pa	I
Parenting Style	Democratic	3,69	3,63	3,82	3,87
	Authoritarian	4,05	3,92	4,13	3,88
	Permissive	3,39	3,35	3,60	3,53

Table 6. Results of the Eta Correlation Test of the Relationship between Parenting Patterns and Adolescents' Learning Interests in the Online Learning Process During the COVID-19 Pandemic (n=63)

Scale	Test	Variable	Value
Nominal * Interval	Eta	Parenting Style	0,479
		Skills	0,261
		Parenting Style	0,486
		Emosi	0,244
		Parenting Style	0,417
		Participation	0,213
		Parenting Style	0,307
		Implemetation	0,213

interest development, influenced by culture, and related to emotions and egocentrism.⁴² Concerning this theory, this study examines interest in learning with four aspects: skills, emotions, participation, and implementation.

The results of the skills subscale found that not all respondents studied regularly, made school schedules, took notes, did assignments, and enjoyed participating in learning. Most did not have a problem with these activities having to be carried out during online learning. The emotion sub-scale found that some respondents stated that they had tried hard to study, found ways and practiced to apply the learning material to life, and found exciting ways to learn. The participation subscale found that most respondents had fun during learning, while on the implementation subscale, most respondents felt satisfied with the final grades. A teenager's emotional maturity is said to be good if they can have self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills.⁴³ Hurlock's theory states that the early adolescent stage is between the ages of 11 and 18. Erikson's psychosocial theory also states that at this stage, adolescents try to find their identity.⁴³

Several factors that can influence interest in learning include the lack of parental involvement.⁴⁴ The role of parents is considered very important in efforts to increase children's interest in learning, one of which is providing support, supervision, and a conducive atmosphere.⁴² The assistance provided by parents indirectly contributes to children's behavior.³² This will also indirectly form positive behavior among several limitations encountered during the learning process.

Parental Characteristics with Adolescent Character Development in Online Learning Process During COVID-19 Pandemic

This study found that the most common parent-child relationship found was with the mother. From a cultural perspective, the role of a mother is to be the child's primary educator.⁴³ Based on several research results, children are more often accompanied by mothers than fathers in the learning process during the COVID-19 pandemic. This is in line with Yang's research (2020), which states that the parenting style brought by mothers has a more significant influence on academic achievement compared to the parenting style given by fathers.³⁶ Taking more time to communicate with children can be used to adjust and find out if there are changes in the child's behavior. Therefore, it is concluded that

parenting can influence the sustainability of children's academics.

Another theory explains that parenting styles between fathers and mothers are different. Psychoanalytic theory argues that mothers have a closer attachment than fathers. In addition, role theory states that mothers are nurturing figures and fathers are the owners of authority and providers in the family. However, the provision of parenting patterns between fathers and mothers has similarities despite the small correlation.⁴⁵ The reciprocal relationship between parents can form the same agreement and belief regarding the parenting patterns that will be applied to children. Parents will provide rational treatment and arrangements to get positive results.

This study found that most of the respondents of adolescent children were girls. A girl's character is more potent than a boy's, in line with a study that found that adolescent girls' character scores were better than adolescent boys'.⁴⁶ However, it is not proven that children's characters are distinguished by gender, but there are differences in how to treat boys and girls.⁴⁷ These results are also in line with previous studies that state that gender is one of the factors that influence learning strategies. It is said that the learning strategies women use are more varied than men's.⁴⁸

Parents in this study were predominantly aged 45-54 years. The more mature the parents are, the better the applied parenting. If parenting patterns are implemented well, it will positively impact adolescent character development.⁴⁶ The interaction created in the relationship between mother and adolescent can increase children's emotional intelligence.⁴³ Evidenced by the study's results on the emotional subscale, some respondents stated that they had tried hard to study, find ways and practice to apply the lesson material to life and find exciting ways to learn. The relationship between mother and adolescent is linked to shaping the character and abilities of adolescents in dealing with demands and expectations from around them.⁴³ The better parents create reciprocal relationships with their children, the more mature the child's emotional intelligence will be.

The study also showed that most respondents came from the lower middle class. Proven by family income ranging from IDR 600,000 to IDR 1,500,000 because the minimum employee income in Bantul is IDR 2,216,463. Economic difficulties can stimulate the ability to adapt for adolescents from underprivileged families.³¹ This is supported by

previous research, which states that, on average, in rural areas, there are many families with low socio-economic status.⁴⁹ Other research studies state that the low socio-economic level of the family influences the close relationship between parents and children.⁴⁶ Underprivileged families can make mothers anxious about establishing relationships with their children.⁵⁰ In addition, parental education factors and family economic status are believed to affect academic achievement.⁵¹ Parental involvement tends to decrease if parent-child communication is not maintained. Ultimately, along with the development of developmental tasks, adolescents will be more comfortable in a social environment than with their families.

Relationship between Parenting Patterns and Adolescents' Interest in Learning in the Online Learning Process During the COVID-19 Pandemic

The finding of the eta correlation test in this study showed a weak relationship between parenting patterns and adolescents' interest in learning. This study's results align with Khairunnisa's (2016) research that parenting patterns have a relationship from sufficient to moderate to adolescents' interest in learning.⁵² Research conducted by Sitanggang (2021) found that parenting patterns affect students' personalities. The personality problem found during the study was the lack of interest in learning in children. This decreased students' reading and writing activities.⁵³ In addition, parental involvement at home has a positive psychosocial effect that can be seen directly in children's prosocial behavior. However, the more parents are involved in their children's learning, the more academic pressure increases, inhibiting their interest and motivation to learn.³ Based on the results above, parenting patterns affect children's academic performance. This also affects academic achievement and final learning outcomes.

Parenting patterns play a role in the continuity of learning because good parenting patterns can positively affect children's emotions.³² Motivating children is one way to help foster children's interest in learning.⁴² On the other hand, parents also need to create a conducive learning environment and atmosphere to encourage increased interest in learning in children of their own accord. This is supported by Henry's opinion (2020) that within the scope of good parental supervision, children can follow lessons and be motivated because they feel that someone supports them during the learning process.⁴⁴ Children's high interest in learning will

encourage children to study diligently in order to get better results.⁵⁰ In addition, parental involvement during the learning process will encourage children to realize their parents' hopes by achieving the best grades and building high ideals.

Based on the research results, democratic parenting patterns are widely applied, followed by permissive parenting patterns, and the least is authoritarian parenting patterns. Authoritarian parenting patterns force children to obey every command of their parents; their implementation tends to be firm and strict, while permissive parenting patterns give the impression of parents who are free toward children because of their minimal role in children's lives.⁵⁴ The application of democratic parenting patterns makes parents pay attention to their child's condition and needs, have an open attitude, and provide positive encouragement for children.⁵⁵ Based on the theory and results above, it can be seen that democratic parenting patterns are applied by knowing the child's interests and motivations in learning. Parents must be responsive and support children to be independent by still giving children freedom but also providing several provisions that must be obeyed.

During the study, the parenting patterns applied came from the closest people who had much free time to accompany children during the child's learning process. Based on the results related to parent-child relationships show that the parenting patterns applied by fathers are democratic and permissive. In contrast, the parenting patterns applied by mothers consist of democratic, permissive, and authoritarian. Parents are more restrictive towards daughters than sons.⁵⁴ However, other studies have found that the parenting patterns applied by mothers have a more significant influence on academic performance than the parenting patterns applied by fathers.³⁶ Tutoring provided by parents, such as affection and attention and helping in solving learning problems, is expected to help children adjust, develop skills, and form habits in learning.⁴ In a descriptive research study conducted by Tanjung (2021) during the COVID-19 period, it was found that during the online learning process, the majority of parents applied a democratic parenting pattern. This is an effort to increase children's interest in learning. The description of its application is accompanying children during learning, providing input, guiding children to solve learning problems, and being open and offering choices related to children's desires in their learning process.⁵⁶ Learning habits that are in line with the learning

outcomes achieved and a high interest in learning will also result in high academic achievement.

Although the study shows a weak relationship between parenting patterns and learning interest, which is in line with the findings of a study that there is a weak significant relationship related to academic performance with parenting patterns.³⁶ However, this must be addressed because this variable is also included in the factors influencing academic performance or learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. Thus, parents need to be aware of the implementation of parenting patterns and children's obedience to the parenting patterns applied by parents so that both understand each other and how parenting patterns can affect children's learning interests.

5. CONCLUSION

Most parenting patterns applied in Wirokerten Village, Banguntapan District, Bantul, are democratic. The results of the bivariate analysis with the eta correlation test obtained a weak relationship between parenting patterns and adolescent interest in the online learning process during the COVID-19 pandemic.

6. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

All authors declared there is no conflict of interest.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author would like to thank all parties who have provided support in the process of compiling and implementing this research.

8. ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

There are no ethical issues. This study was approved by the Health Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Health Sciences Universitas Brawijaya.

REFERENCES

- Viner RM, Bonell C, Drake L, Jourdan D, Davies N, Baltag V, et al. Reopening schools during the COVID-19 pandemic: Governments must balance the uncertainty and risks of reopening schools against the clear harms associated with prolonged closure. *Arch Dis Child*. 2020;0(0):1–3.
- United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF). *Situasi Anak di Indonesia - Tren, peluang, dan Tantangan dalam Memenuhi Hak-Hak Anak*. Unicef Indones. 2020;8–38.
- Yulia A, Juwandani E, Maulidya D. Model Pembelajaran Kooperatif Learning. *Semin Nas Ilmu Pendidik dan Multi Disiplin*. 2020;223–7.
- Abidah A, Hidaayatullaah HN, Simamora RM, Fehabutar D, Mutakinati L, Suprpto N. The Impact of Covid-19 to Indonesian Education and Its Relation to the Philosophy of "Merdeka Belajar." *Stud Philos Sci Educ*. 2020;1(1):38–49.
- Irfan I. Akuntansi Zakat Perusahaan: Perspektif Cendekiawan Muslim Di Kota Medan. *J Ris Akunt dan Bisnis*. 2020;20(1):51–60.
- Mishra L, Gupta T, Shree A. Online teaching-learning in higher education during lockdown period of COVID-19 pandemic. *Int J Educ Res Open*. 2020;
- Rasmitadila. *Penyelenggaraan pendidikan inklusi*. Raja Grafindo Persada; 2020.
- Sari I, Syatriana E, Rum EP. the Students' Perception Towards the Effectiveness of Speaking for Intermediate Subject To Support Their Speaking Skill of English Department Students in Makassar Muhammadiyah University. *J Lang Test Assess*. 2021;1(2):209–17.
- Fitria L, Ildil I. Kecemasan Remaja pada Masa Pandemi Covid-19. *J Pendidik Indones*. 2020;6(1):1–4.
- Son C, Hegde S, Smith A, Wang X, Sasangohar F. Effects of COVID-19 on college students' mental health in the United States: Interview survey study. *J Med Internet Res*. 2020;22(9):1–14.
- Fauziyyah R, Awinda RC, Besral B. Dampak Pembelajaran Jarak Jauh terhadap Tingkat Stres dan Kecemasan Mahasiswa selama Pandemi COVID-19. *J Biostat Kependudukan, dan Inform Kesehatan*. 2021;1(2):113.
- Hasanah U, Edwita, Januar A. Pelatihan Pengembangan Digital Assesment Bagi Guru Sekolah Dasar Di Kepulauan Seribu. *BERNAS J Pengabdian Kpd Masyarakat*. 2020;1(4):338–46.
- Hakim MSHI. Implementasi Kolaborasi Orang Tua dan Guru Dalam Pelaksanaan Pembelajaran Daring pada PAUD. *JIEES J Islam Educ Elem Sch*. 2020;1(1):26–33.
- Wardani A, Ayriza Y. Analisis Kendala Orang Tua dalam Mendampingi Anak Belajar di Rumah Pada Masa Pandemi Covid-19. *J Obs J*

- Pendidik Anak Usia Dini. 2021;5(1):772.
15. Putri YS, Pratiwi IA, Ismaya EA. Peran Pola Asuh Dalam Pembentukan Minat Belajar Anak Di Desa Medini. *J Muara Pendidik*. 2020;5(2):697–704.
 16. Lie A, Tamah SM, Gozali I, Triwidayati KR, Utami TSD, Jemadi F. Secondary School Language Teachers' Online Learning Engagement During the Covid-19 Pandemic in Indonesia. *J Inf Technol Educ Res*. 2020;19:803–32.
 17. Di Petro G. The impact of Covid-19 on student achievement: Evidence from a recent meta-analysis. *Educ Res Rev*. 2023;
 18. Oyedotun TD. Sudden change of pedagogy in education driven by COVID-19: Perspectives and evaluation from a developing country. *Res Glob [Internet]*. 2020;2. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resglo.2020.100029>
 19. Purwanto A, Asbari M, Fahlevi M, Mufid A, Agistiawati E, Cahyono Y, et al. Impact of work from home (wfh) on indonesian teachers performance during the Covid-19 pandemic : an exploratory study. *Int J Adv Sci Technol*. 2020;29(5):6235–44.
 20. Rinawati D, Darisman EK. Survei tingkat kejenuhan siswa SMK belajar di rumah pada mata pelajaran produk kreatif dan kewirausahaan selama masa pandemi covid-19. *J Sci Educ*. 2020;1(1):32–40.
 21. Susanto S. Efektifitas Small Group Discussion Dengan Model Problem Based Learning Dalam Pembelajaran Di Masa Pandemi Covid-19. *J Pendidik Mod*. 2020;6(1):55–60.
 22. Hidayah AN. Pengaruh terapi aktivitas kelompok stimulasi persepsi sensori terhadap kemampuan mengontrol halusinasi pada pasien halusinasi di rsjd dr amino gondohutomo semarang. *Fikkes J keperawatan*. 2015;8(1):44–55.
 23. Cahyani A, Listiana iin D, Larasati SPD. Motivasi Belajar Siswa Man Binjai Pada Pembelajaran Daring Di Masa Pandemi Covid-19. *J Pendidik Islam*. 2020;2(1):123–40.
 24. Nurhasanah S, Sobandi A. Minat belajar sebagai determinan hasil belajar siswa (learning interest as determinant student learning outcomes). *J Pendidik Manaj Perkantoran [Internet]*. 2016;1(1):128–35. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.17509/jpm.v1i1.3264>
 25. Korompot S, Rahim M, Pakaya R. Persepsi Siswa Tentang Faktor yang Mempengaruhi Minat Belajar. *JAMBURA Guid Couns J*. 2020;1(1):40–8.
 26. Nuuru HRA, Pratiwi A. Efektivitas terapi musik sebagai intervensi mengontrol halusinasi pendengaran: case report. *J Keperawatan Jiwa*. 2024;12(2):297–304.
 27. Apritia CK, Barnadib SI. Hubungan Pola Asuh Orang Tua Dengan minat belajar siswa sekolah dasar muhammadiyah jogokariyan yogyakarta. *J Kel*. 2015;1(2):196–203.
 28. Ayun Q. Pola Asuh Orang Tua dan Metode Pengasuhan dalam Membentuk Kepribadian Anak. *ThufuLA J Inov Pendidik Guru Raudhatul Athfal*. 2017;5(1):102.
 29. Fadhilah TN, Andayani DEH, Rofian. Analisis Pola Asuh Orang Tua Terhadap Motivasi Belajar Siswa. *J Pedagogi dan Pembelajaran*. 2022;2(2):249–55.
 30. Makhruzah S, Putri VS, Yanti RD. Pengaruh penerapan strategi pelaksanaan perilaku kekerasan terhadap tanda gejala klien skizofrenia di rumah sakit jiwa daerah provinsi jambi. *J Akad Baiturrahim Jambi*. 2021;10(1):39–46.
 31. Kustiah S. Hubungan Pola Asuh Orang Tua terhadap Kemandirian Anak. *J EST*. 2020;2(3):152–60.
 32. Anggraeni D, Rezki JF, Barat J. Dampak pembelajaran jarak jauh selama pandemi covid-19 terhadap hasil belajar siswa SMA di Indonesia. *J Ilm Ekon Bisnis*. 2024;29(2):175–91.
 33. Safitri YA, Baedowi S, Setianingsih ES. Pola Asuh Orang Tua di Era Digital Berpengaruh Dalam Membentuk Karakter Kedisiplinan Belajar Siswa Kelas IV. *Mimb PGSD Undiksha*. 2020;8(3):508–14.
 34. Masni H. Peran pola asuh demokratis orangtua terhadap pengembangan potensi diri dan kreativitas siswa. *J Ilm Dikdaya*. 2017;6(1):58–74.
 35. Estlein R. Parenting as a Communication Process: Integrating Interpersonal Communication Theory and Parenting Styles Conceptualization. *J Fam Theory Rev*. 2021;13(1):21–33.
 36. Candelanza AL, Buot EQC, Merin JA. Diana Baumrind ' s Parenting Style and Child ' s Academic Performance : A Tie-. *Psychol Educ*. 2021;58(5):1497–502.
 37. Firmansyah W. Pengaruh Pola Asuh Orang Tua Terhadap Pembentukan Karakter Anak.

- Prim Educ J silampari. 2019;1(1):621–9.
38. Nur Utami AC, Raharjo ST. Pola Asuh Orang Tua Dan Kenakalan Remaja. *Focus J Pekerj Sos.* 2021;4(1):1–15.
 39. Apriyanto M., Herlina L. Analisis Prestasi Belajar Matematika pada Masa Pandemi Ditinjau dari Minat Belajar Siswa. *Pros Semin Nas dan Disk Panel Pendidik Mat Univ Indraprasta PGRI.* 2020;(80):135–44.
 40. Hidayatullah H, Gusniwati G, Buhaerah B. Pengaruh pembelajaran daring terhadap minat belajar siswa kelas vii mts yasrib batu-batu pada masa covid-19. *Pi Math Educ J.* 2021;4(1):1–9.
 41. Siregar S, Nazliah R, Hasibuan R, Julyanti E, Siregar M, Junita. Manajemen Peningkatan Kualitas Pembelajaran Matematika Pada Sma Labuhanbatu. *J Educ Dev.* 2021;9(2):285–90.
 42. Elizabeth M, Ramírez H. Communicative Language Teaching Strategies to Develop Senior High School Students' English Language Speaking Skill. *J Res Sch Prof English Lang Teach.* 2023;7(35).
 43. Ramadhianti N, Alfiasari A. Temperamen, Interaksi Ibu-Remaja, dan Kecerdasan Emosi Remaja Pada Keluarga dengan Ibu Bekerja di Perdesaan. *J Ilmu Kel dan Konsum.* 2017;10(2):132–42.
 44. Fitri Yanti N, Sumianto. Analisis Faktor-Faktor yang Menghambat Minat Belajar Dimasa Pandemi Covid-19 pada Siswa SDN 008 Salo. *J Pendidik Tambusai.* 2021;5(1):608–14.
 45. Kuppens S, Ceulemans E. Parenting Styles: A Closer Look at a Well-Known Concept. *J Child Fam Stud.* 2019;28(1):168–81.
 46. Situmorang ZR, Hastuti D, Herawati T. Pengaruh Kelekatan dan Komunikasi dengan Orang Tua terhadap Karakter Remaja Perdesaan. *J Ilmu Kel dan Konsum.* 2016;9(2):113–23.
 47. Novita L, Hastuti D, Herawati T. Pengaruh iklim keluarga dan keteladanan orang tua terhadap karakter remaja pedesaan. *J Pendidik Karakter.* 2015;5(2):184–94.
 48. Bun Y, Taib B, Mufidatul Ummah D. Analisis Pola Asuh Otoriter Orang Tua Terhadap Perkembangan Moral Anak. *J Ilm Cahaya Paud.* 2020;2(1):128–37.
 49. Khusaini M. Prestasi Belajar dan Karakteristik Orang Tua: Studi Perbandingan Sekolah Menengah Atas Perkotaan-Pedesaan. *J Pendidik Ekon Undiksha.* 2020;12(2):296–310.
 50. Sari SL, Devianti R, Safitri Nur'aini. Kelekatan Orangtua untuk Pembentukan untuk Pembentukan Karakter Anak. *Educ Guid Couns Dev J.* 2018;1(1):17–31.
 51. Citrandini M, Hernawati N. Emosi akademik, Strategi Belajar, dan Prestasi Akademik Siswa SMA di Wlayah Perdesaan. *J Ilmu Kel dan Konsum.* 2016;9(3):195–205.
 52. Khairunnisa A, Kurniatin N. Hubungan Pola Asuh Orang Tua Dengan Minat Belajar Remaja Pada Kejar Paket B Di Pkbm Mutiara Bangsa Kecamatan Dramaga Kabupaten Bogor. *J Teknol Pendidik.* 2016;5(1):155–68.
 53. Sitanggang R. Peran Guru Bimbingan dan Konseling dalam Meningkatkan Motivasi Belajar Siswa di Era COVID-19 (Studi Literatur). *Edukatif J Ilmu Pendidik.* 2021;3(6):5101–8.
 54. Kusmiati E, Sari DY, Mutiara S. Pola Asuh Orang Tua Dalam Membentuk Disiplin Anak Di Masa Pandemi. *PERNIK J Pendidik Anak Usia Dini [Internet].* 2021;4(2):78–93. Available from: <https://jurnal.univpgri-palembang.ac.id/index.php/pernik/article/view/5424>
 55. Rohmania A, Setiawan D, Khamdun K. Pola Asuh Demokratis Orang Tua Dalam Memberikan Motivasi Belajar Siswa Selama Masa Pandemi Covid-19. *Prim J Pendidik Guru Sekol Dasar.* 2021;10(6):1610.
 56. Tanjung R. Pengajaran di sd negeri 118273 mampang kecamatan kotapinang kabupaten labuhan batu selatan. *Dirasatul Ibtidaiyah.* 2021;1(1):98–110.